

A Classical Insight into *Kshara Kalpana*: Textual Compilation and Enumeration of different *Kshara*

Jeel Patel¹, Dr. Bharti Umretia²

¹PG Scholar, Upgraded Department of Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Government Ayurved College, Vadodara, Gujarat

²Reader and Head Upgraded Department of Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Government Ayurved College, Vadodara, Gujarat

Corresponding Author: Jeel Patel

ABSTRACT: *Kshara Kalpana* is a unique and potent dosage form in Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals, primarily derived from plant materials and occasionally from animal derivatives, processed to extract their alkaline substances. The present study aims to explore the textual compilation and analysis of *Kshara Kalpana* and enumeration of different *Kshara* with their name of formulation and indications from 15 classical texts of Ayurveda compendium. Acharya Sushruta was the first to systematically elaborate on various aspects of this dosage form including its pharmaceutical description as well as its therapeutic application. The analysis revealed a total of 106 plant-origin *Kshara* and 18 animal-origin *Kshara*, reflecting the wide documentation of this dosage form across classical literature. The selection of plants or animal derivatives may not arbitrary but guided by their alkaline rich components, therapeutic efficacy and pharmaceutical feasibility. This screening highlighted the vast documentation of various *Kshara* in classical Ayurvedic texts. Accordingly, this review offers valuable insights into the evaluation of this dosage form and identifies potential avenues for future research on different *Kshara*.

KEYWORDS: *Kshara*, Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals, alkaline substances

INTRODUCTION

Kshara Kalpana is a unique dosage form among the classical Ayurvedic dosage form, used for various therapeutic and pharmaceutical approaches. *Kshara* refers to an alkaline substance obtained from the ashes of plant (i.e. *Yava*, *Apamarga*), animal (i.e. *Goshakrita Kshara*, *Mayurapadanala Kshara*), or mineral origin (i.e. *Tankana*, *Navasagara*, *Surya Kshara*). It is classified as *Audabhida Dravya* (plant originated substance) but several *Kshara* of animal origin are also found in classical literature. It represents a unique and highly valued dosage form in Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals, renowned for its corrosive nature. Extensive descriptions of *Kshara* and its pharmaceutical preparations are preserved in Ayurvedic compendia, detailing methods of preparation, confirmatory tests, properties, *Rasapanchaka*, indications, contraindications, dose, *Anupana*, shelf life, classification and clinical applications. The earliest comprehensive pharmaceutical account was described by Acharya Sushruta, who presented it as a superior surgical adjunct. He was also the first to mention the plant materials employed in its preparation. Over time, the concepts outlined in the Samhita were expanded in later classical texts, leading to the development of numerous varieties of *Kshara* derived from various natural products, with wide applications in diverse therapeutic contexts.

In Ayurveda, it is not only used as a single drug (i.e. *Yava Kshara*, *Talapushpa Kshara*) but is also incorporated into various dosage forms (i.e. *Kshara Ghrita*,¹ *Kshara Gutika*²) and serves as an ingredient in numerous formulations (*Shankha Vati*,³ *Narayana Churna*⁴). It is administered internally in conditions such as *Arsha*, *Mutraroga*, *Yakrita-Pliha Roga*, *Gulma*, *Grahani*, *Anaha* and others. Externally, it is applied in disorders like *Svitra*, *Netraroga*, *Arbuda*, *Bahyarsha*, etc. Classical texts described many different alkaline rich plant for *Kshara* preparation either used individually or as components in the preparation of other formulations. In addition to plant-derived varieties, various animal-sourced *Kshara* are also documented, along with their respective therapeutic utilities.

In light of the aforementioned context, the present review aims to compile and analyze classical textual descriptions of *Kshara* along with their various sources, either in the form of compound formulations or as single drugs, which are used internally, externally, or by both routes of administration. This compilation highlights the diverse origins and therapeutic applications of *Kshara*, providing a valuable foundation for further research in this field.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For this review, 15 classical texts such as Charaka Samhita, Susruta Samhita, Kashyapa Samhita, Harita Samhita, Bhela Samhita, Ashtanga Samgraha, Ashtanga Hridaya, Chakradatta, Vangasena Samhita, Gadanigraha, Sharangadhara Samhita, Bhavaprakasha Samhita, Yogatarangini, Yogaratnakara and Bhaishjya Ratnavali were screened for descriptions related to *Kshara*. In all texts total number and name of *Kshara Dravya* found in the reviewed texts were extracted along with their detailed information regarding name of formulation and indication with their reference. The inclusion and exclusion criteria for the selection of *Kshara Dravya* from different texts are mentioned below.

Inclusion criteria

1. Plant and animal origin single *Kshara* in which the term *Kshara* appears as a suffix or prefix in the name (i.e. *Tila Kshara*, *Yava Kshhara*, *Gomaya Kshara*)
2. Compound formulations containing any *Kshara Dravya* as an ingredient (i.e. *Agnika Ghrita*, *Chavikadi Ghrita*)
3. Any drug mentioned as a source for *Kshara* (i.e. *Danti Kshara* is mentioned as *Pratinidhi Dravya* for *Chitraka* but not mentioned as any formulation in particular text)

Exclusion Criteria

1. *Kshara Dravya* that are repeated within a particular text (i.e. In Astanga Samgraha, *Yava Kshara* is used as a single *Kshara* and other formulation such as *Dadhika Ghrita*, *Hingavadi Ghrita*, *Trilavanadi Yoga*, etc., only one among them was selected as the source of *Kshara*.)
2. Singal/ Compound formulations in which only *Bhasma* (ash) of particular drug used as *Kshara* (i.e. In Charaka Samhita, only *Bhasma* of mentioned ingredients are used in *Bhunimbadi Kshara*, *Haridradi Kshara* etc./ In preparation of *Ksharavaleha* / *Kshara Guda Bhasma* of mentioned ingredients are used which are excluded.)
3. Naturally occurring minerals considered as *Kshara* (e.g., *Tankana*, *Suryakshara* etc.)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Textual compilation of *Kshara Kalpana* along with the enumeration of different *Kshara Samhita Kala Charaka Samhita*

Acharya Charaka illustrate the definition, properties, characteristics and applications of *Kshara*. It is comprehended by its “*Ksharanata*” property and is composed of multiple *Rasa* (tastes) with a predominance of *Katu* and *Lavana Rasa*.⁵

Kshara is classified as one of the *Shashtra Pranidhana Chikitsa* (surgical treatment) within the three primary categories of *Chikitsa*.⁶ It is also classified as *Audbhidha Dravya* (plant based drugs) in *Sutra Sthana*, where substances are grouped into three main categories based on their origin.⁷ It is also included in *Katu Skandha Dravya* in *Vimana Sthana*.⁸ *Atisevanajanya Dosha* of *Kshara* is also mentioned in *Vimana Sthana*.⁹

Approximately 24 plant-based *Kshara* and 9 animal-origin *Kshara* are listed in this text, as mentioned in table no.1.

Table No.1: Different *Kshara* mentioned in Charaka Samhita

Sr.no	Name of <i>Kshara</i>	Name of Formulation	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Svarjika Kshara</i>	<i>Krimighna Yavagu</i>	<i>Krimi</i>	Su. 2/23
2.	<i>Tila Kshara</i>	<i>Haridradi Lepa</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	Su. 3/14
3.	<i>Utpalanala Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Raktapita</i>	Chi. 4/93
4.	<i>Mrunala, Padma, Utpala Keshara, Priyangu, Madhooka, Asana Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Raktapita</i>	Chi. 4/94
5.	<i>Yava Kshara</i>	<i>Kshirashatapala Ghrita</i>	<i>Gulma, Grahani, Pandu</i>	Chi. 5/147
6.	<i>Kadali Kshara</i>	<i>Kadali Ksharadi Lepa</i>	<i>Svitra</i>	Chi. 7/168
7.	<i>Malati Koraka Kshara</i>	<i>Hastimadadi Lepa</i>	<i>Svitra</i>	Chi. 7/169
8.	<i>Aja Karisha Kshara</i>	<i>Kshara Vatika</i>	<i>Shotha, Grahani, Jalodara</i>	Chi. 13/162165
9.	<i>Bilva Kshara</i>	<i>Kshara Taila</i>	<i>Udararoga, Hridaroga</i>	Chi. 13/169170
10.	<i>Agnimantha, Shyonaka, Bala, Apamarga, Palasha Kshara</i>	<i>Kshara Taila</i>	<i>Udararoga, Vatavikara</i>	Chi. 13/170171
11.	<i>Ashvagandha Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Svasa</i>	Chi. 17/117
12.	<i>Mayurapadanala, Shallka Shakala, Kurara Roma, Chasha Roma, Aja-Avi Ashthi, Ek-Dvishapha Charma, Ashthi, Khura Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Svasa</i>	Chi. 17/117-119
13.	<i>Eranda Patra, Surasa Patra Kshara</i>	<i>Leha Yoga</i>	<i>Kasa</i>	Chi. 18/171
14.	<i>Mushkaka Kshara</i>	<i>Kshara Gutika</i>	<i>Visha</i>	Chi.26/192193
15.	<i>Shushka Mulaka Kshara</i>	<i>Kshara Taila</i>	<i>Karnaroga</i>	Chi.26/226

Sushruta Samhita

A separate chapter of *Ksharapakavidhi* is mentioned in *Sutra Sthana* of this text. This chapter provides comprehensive details on the definition, characteristics, types, preparation methods, as well as *Guna, Dosha,*

Kshara Pariksha, *Rasapanchaka*, *Yogya* (indications), *Ayogya* (contraindications), and the therapeutic applications of *Kshara*.¹⁰

Kshara is regarded as more significant than *Shastra* and *Anushashtra* due to its *Chhedana*, *Bhedana*, *Lekhana Karma*, and ability to alleviate *Tridosha*.¹¹

According to the administration, two types of *Kshara* are mentioned, *Paniya* and *Pratisaraniya*. *Pratisaraniya Kshara* is further classified into three categories based on its alkalinity: *Mridu*, *Madhyama* and *Tikshana*. The preparation methods and *Kshara Pariksha* for these three types are explained in detail. Additionally, the applications of *Pratisaraniya Kshara*, as well as the characteristics of *Ksharadagdha*, *Samyakadagdha*, *Hinadagdha*, and *Atidagdha*, are also mentioned.

Mula, *Patra*, and *Shakha* of about 23 plants are burnt for *Kshara* preparation, as described in *Ksharapaka Vidhi Adhyaya*,¹² which are listed in table no. 2.

Table No.2: Listing of Plants used for *Kshara* preparation mentioned in *Susrhuta Samhita*

Sr.no	Name of Plant	Sr.no	Name of Plant	Sr.no	Name of Plant
1.	<i>Kutaja</i>	2.	<i>Palasha</i>	3.	<i>Ashvakarna</i>
4.	<i>Paribhadra</i>	5.	<i>Bibhitaki</i>	6.	<i>Aragavadha</i>
7.	<i>Tilvaka</i>	8.	<i>Arka</i>	9.	<i>Snuhi</i>
10.	<i>Apamarga</i>	11.	<i>Patala</i>	12.	<i>Naktamala</i>
13.	<i>Vrusha</i>	14.	<i>Kadali</i>	15.	<i>Chitraka</i>
16.	<i>Putika</i>	17.	<i>Indravrusha</i>	18.	<i>Asphota</i>
19.	<i>Ashvamaraka</i>	20.	<i>Saptachhada</i>	21.	<i>Agnimantha</i>
22.	<i>Gunja</i>	23.	<i>Koshataki</i>		

Apart from these 23 plants, some other *Kshara* are also mentioned in *Chikitsa* of various diseases which are listed in table no.3.

Table No.3: Different *Kshara* mentioned in *Sushruta Samhita*

Sr.no	Name of <i>Kshara</i>	Name of Formulation	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Yava Kshara</i>	<i>Shodhana Varti</i>	<i>Vrana Shodhana</i>	Su. 36/14
2.	<i>Svarjika Kshara</i>	<i>Hingavadi Churna</i>	<i>Kasa, Svasa, Hridaroga</i>	Chi.5/28
3.	<i>Samudra Shukti, Parijata, Ikshuraka (Kokilaksha), Putikaranja Kshara</i>	<i>Pliharoga Yoga</i>	<i>Pliharoga</i>	Chi.14/13
4.	<i>Kakadani, Kakajangha, Bruhati, Kantakari, Lamba, Kadambapushpi, Mandari, Shukanasa Kshara</i>	<i>Paniya Kshara Yoga</i>	<i>Shlipada</i>	Chi.20/63
5.	<i>Dravanti, Trivruta, Danti, Nili, Shyama, Saptala, Shankhini Kshara</i>	<i>Shlipadahara Kshara Yoga</i>	<i>Shlipada</i>	Chi.20/68

Kashyapa Samhita

A detailed description of is not mentioned. *Yava Kshara* and *Svarjika Kshara* are used as an ingredient in different formulations.¹³

Harita Samhita

The characteristics and actions of *Kshara* are mentioned as *Vidahi*, *Ushna*, and *Kledi Guna*. It is used in conditions such as *Shula*, *Aruchi*, *Trusha*, and *Mutrakrichchha*.¹⁴ *Kshara Karma* is included in the list of the eight types of treatment.¹⁵ The dose of *Kshara Aushadhi* is also mentioned as *Ardhapala* (24 g).¹⁶ About 28 *Kshara* are found in this text as listed in table no.4.

Table No.4: Different *Kshara* mentioned in Harita Samhita

Sr.no	Name of <i>Kshara</i>	Name of Formulation	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Mushkaka, Palasha, Arjuna, Dhava, Jivanti, Apamarga, Tila, Rajani, Kanaka, Vasa, Kushmanda valli</i>	<i>Ksharamrita</i>	<i>Shula, Vibandha, Anaha, Kaphaja Roga, Krimi</i>	3/4/16
2.	<i>Kadali Kshara</i>	<i>Kadalijala Panaka</i>	<i>Ajirna</i>	3/4/28
3.	<i>Yava, Svarjika Kshara</i>	<i>Brihadahingu Churna</i>	<i>Shula, Anaha, Vibandha</i>	3/7/35
4.	<i>Surana, Jivaka, Mudga, Palasha, Kokilaksha</i>	<i>Ksharadaha Yoga</i>	<i>Arsha</i>	3/11/103
5.	<i>Shukti, Vishala, Kokila, Shati, Jaya (Arani)</i>	<i>Ksharapana Yoga</i>	<i>Gulma, Anaha, Vibandha, Shula</i>	3/26/39
6.	<i>Aranya Gomaya Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Upsarga</i>	3/34/16
7.	<i>Arka, Bhallataka, Masha Kshara</i>	<i>Tilaksharadi Lepa</i>	<i>Visha</i>	3/41/13

Bhela Samhita

Acharya Bhela has described the qualities of all *Kshara* and *Lavana* as *Dipaniya*, *Avrushya* and contraindicated in *Durbala Purusha*¹⁷ and furthermore he highlights the specific properties of *Yavanala Kshara* and *Svadamstra Kshara* as being *Shita* in nature and harmful for the *Netra*.¹⁸ He has also mentioned that *Kshara* can be harmful to the body if it is taken for a long duration.¹⁹

Table No.5: Different *Kshara* mentioned in Bhela Samhita

Sr.no	Name of <i>Kshara</i>	Name of Formulation	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Pippali, Nagara Kshara</i>	<i>Shulahara Yoga</i>	<i>Shula</i>	Su. 10/19
2.	<i>Yava, Svadamstra Kshara</i>	-	-	Su. 28/16
3.	<i>Svarjika Kshara</i>	<i>Ksharagada</i>	<i>Visha</i>	Chi. 5/41
4.	<i>Danti, Arjuna Kshara</i>	<i>Danti Ksharadi Yoga</i>	<i>Jathararoga</i>	Chi. 16/28

Samgraha Kala

Ashtanga Samgraha

A dedicated chapter in *Sutra Sthana* explores various aspects of *Kshara*, including its properties, preparatory methods, types, contraindications, and the procedure for its application. It also covers *Ksharavibhrama Lakshana* and the corresponding treatment.²⁰

Table No. 6: Different *Kshara* mentioned in Ashtanga Samgraha

Sr.no	Name of <i>Kshara</i>	Name of Formulation	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Utpalanala, Mrinala, Ambhoja Kinjalaka, Shyama, Asana, Madhuka Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Raktapita</i>	Chi. 3/70
2.	<i>Svarjika Kshara</i>	<i>Agni Ghrita</i>	<i>Grahani</i>	Chi. 12/7
3.	<i>Dashamula, Arkamula, Danti, Trivruta, Patha, Chitraka, Asphota,</i>	<i>Dashamuladi Gulika</i>	<i>Grahani</i>	Chi. 12/17
	<i>Rasna, Snuhikanda Kshara</i>			
4.	<i>Patala, Paribhadra Kshara</i>	<i>Mutraghatahara Yoga</i>	<i>Mutraghata</i>	Chi. 13/5
5.	<i>Gramyapashu Shakruta Kshara</i>	<i>Ksharavaleha</i>	<i>Ashmari</i>	Chi. 13/16
6.	<i>Kadali, Apamarga, Palasha, Kaunchapakshi Ashthi, Karavira Kshara</i>	<i>Tila Ksharadi Leha</i>	<i>Ashmari</i>	Chi. 13/17
7.	<i>Hasti, Sukara, Khara, Ushtra Ashthi Kshara</i>	<i>Pramehahara Yoga</i>	<i>Vataja Prameha</i>	Chi. 14/8
8.	<i>Yava Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Yoniroga</i>	Chi. 16/48
9.	<i>Samudra Shukti Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Plihodara</i>	Chi. 17/33
10.	<i>Gajamala Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Svitra</i>	Chi. 22/22
11.	<i>Tilanala Kshara</i>	<i>Rasakriya Yoga</i>	<i>Netraroga</i>	Ut. 14/8
12.	<i>Narikela Ashthi, Bhallataka, Tala, Vamsha, Karira Kshara</i>	<i>Anjana Yoga</i>	<i>Shukla Roga</i>	Ut. 14/42
13.	<i>Adari, Kakajangha, Kakadani, Shukanasa, Kadambapushpa, Brihatidvaya Kshara</i>	<i>Adaryadi Kshara Yoga</i>	<i>Slipada, Apachi, Grahani, Visha, Arochaka</i>	Ut. 35/21
14.	<i>Aja Shakruta Kshara</i>	<i>Svarjikadi Lepa</i>	<i>Visharoga</i>	Ut. 43/51
15.	<i>Rushabha Kshara</i>	<i>Yava Ksharadi Yoga</i>	<i>Chhachhundara Visha</i>	Ut. 46/48

Ashtanga Hridaya

A detailed description related to *Kshara* is mentioned in the chapter named “*Ksharagnikarmavidhi*” in *Sutra Sthana* of this text. The preparatory method of *Kshara* is almost similar to that of Ashtanga Samgraha. *Kshara Prayoga Vidhi* on *Arsha*, *Vartma Roga*, *Nasarsha* and *Karnarsha* also described in detail.²¹

Table No.7: Different *Kshara* mentioned in Ashtanga Hridaya

Sr.no	Name of <i>Kshara</i>	Name of Formulation	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Yava Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Makkala Shula</i>	Sha.1/92
2.	<i>Utpalanala, Ambhoja, Shyama, Madhooka Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Grathita Raktapita</i>	Chi.2/46
3.	<i>Svarjika Kshara</i>	<i>Chavikadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Kshayaja Kasa</i>	Chi.3/161
4.	<i>Erandapatra, Surasapatra Kshara</i>	<i>Kasahara Yoga</i>	<i>Kasa</i>	Chi.3/170
5.	<i>Apamarga Kshara</i>	<i>Tilaksharadi Yoga</i>	<i>Ashmari</i>	Chi.11/31
6.	<i>Bilva Kshara</i>	<i>Bilva Kshara Taila</i>	<i>Udararoga</i>	Chi. 15/46
7.	<i>Tintuka, Bala, Tarkari, Tilanala, Palasha Kshara</i>	<i>Siddha Taila Yoga</i>	<i>Udararoga</i>	Chi.15/46
8.	<i>Samudrashukti Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Udararoga</i>	Chi.15/86
9.	<i>Naktamala (Putikaranja) Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Udararoga</i>	Chi.15/86
10.	<i>Kadali, Kshuraka (Kokilaksha) Kshara</i>	<i>Kadalyadi Taila</i>	<i>Pliharoga</i>	Chi. 15/95
11.	<i>Chhaga Karisha Kshara</i>	<i>Kshara Gutika</i>	<i>Ajirna, Shotha, Udararoga</i>	Chi.15/103
12.	<i>Hatha Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Mukharoga</i>	Ut. 22/70

Chakradatta

A detailed explanation of the preparation methods for *Kshara Sadhana Vidhi*, *Pratisaraniya Kshara*,²² *Paniya Kshara*²³ along with *Ksharapaka Pariksha* are described²⁴ in *Arsha Chikitsa*.²⁵ Reference of *Kalamushkaka Kshara* is mentioned in a preparation of *Ksharapaka*. *Snuhi Kshara* is used for *Gandhamarjara Shodhana*. *Pana* of *Ketaki Kshara* with *Taila* is mentioned in *Vataja Gulma Chikitsa*, and *Talapushpa Kshara* with *Guda* is used in *Pliharoga Chikitsa*. Approximately 21 *Kshara* are found in this text as listed below.

Table No.8: Different *Kshara* mentioned in Chakradatta

Sr.no	Name of <i>Kshara</i>	Name of Formulation	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Yava Kshara</i>	<i>Kutaja Avaleha</i>	<i>Atisara</i>	3/84
2.	<i>Apamarga Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Lingarsha</i>	5/10
3.	<i>Palasha Kshara</i>	<i>Vyoshadhya Ghrita</i>	<i>Arsha</i>	5/103
4.	<i>Kalamushkaka Kshara</i>	-	-	5/138

5.	<i>Tilanalā, Shigrū, Kokilaksha, Palasha, Beeja Kshara</i>	<i>Brihadā Agnimukha Churna</i>	<i>Agnimandhya</i>	6/33
6.	<i>Snuhi Kshara</i>	-	-	20/292
7.	<i>Ketaki Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Vataja Gulma</i>	30/13
8.	<i>Talapushpa Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Yakrita Pliha Roga</i>	38/4
9.	<i>Putikaranja Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Yakrita Pliha Roga</i>	38/5
10.	<i>Samudra Shukti Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Yakrita Pliha Roga</i>	38/6
11.	<i>Shushka Mulaka Kshara</i>	<i>Kshara Gutika</i>	<i>Shotha</i>	39/36
12.	<i>Gajalindaja Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Svitra</i>	50/71
13.	<i>Svarjika Kshara</i>	<i>Svarjika Kshara Taila</i>	<i>Badhirya, Karnanada</i>	57/26
14.	<i>Tala, Narikela, Karira, Bhallataka, Vansha Kshara</i>	<i>Talaksharadhyanjana</i>	<i>Shukrarma</i>	59/79

Vangasena Samhita

Acharya Vangasena mentioned the preparatory method of *Kshara* along with its types and properties in this text.²⁶

Table No.9: Different *Kshara* mentioned in Vangasena Samhita

Sr.no	Name of <i>Kshara</i>	Name of Formulation	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Kadali, Tila, Kshuraka Kshara</i>	<i>Taila Yoga</i>	<i>Kaphavataja Roga, Pliharoga</i>	11/191
2.	<i>Lodhra, Chitraka, Varuna, Shigrumula, Vatyala, Punarnava, Manakanda, Brahmanayastika, Pushkara</i>	<i>Brihadakshara Pippali</i>	<i>Pliharoga, Gulma, Ajinrna</i>	11/206
3.	<i>Vanakarisha (Gomaya) Kshara</i>	<i>Kshara Vatika</i>	<i>Jalodara</i>	11/232
4.	<i>Yava, Svarjika Kshara</i>	<i>Panchamuladi Ghrita</i>	<i>Shula, Gulma, Udararoga</i>	20/44
5.	<i>Arjuna Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Jathararoga</i>	20/189
6.	<i>Bala Mulaka, Shunthi Kshara</i>	<i>Kshara Taila</i>	<i>Krimi, Karnaroga</i>	34/65

Gadanigraha

The unique preparatory method of *Ksharapaka*, along with *Ksharapaka Lakshana* has been described by Acharya Shodhala.²⁷ Additionally, *Ksharapatana Vidhi* and *Kshara Vibhrama Chikitsa* are also explained in this text.²⁸ Furthermore, *Kshara* is also included in *Shophadarana Varga Dravya*.²⁹

Table No.10: Different *Kshara* mentioned in *Gadanigraha*

Sr.no	Name of <i>Kshara</i>	Name of Formulation	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Svarjika Kshara</i>	<i>Guggulutikta Ghrita</i>	<i>Galaganda, Ajirna, Shula</i>	1/1/203
2.	<i>Chavya, Yava, Chitraka Kshara</i>	<i>Sumukhadhya Taila</i>	<i>Arsha</i>	2/4/134
3.	<i>Mushkaka Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	-	2/4/172
4.	<i>Snuhi Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Arsha</i>	2/4/173
5.	<i>Padma, Utpala, Palasha, Dhava, Himstra, Kumuda Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Grathita Raktapita</i>	2/8/51-53
6.	<i>Kushtha, Ketaki, Svarjika Kshara</i>	<i>Gulmahara Yoga</i>	<i>Vataja Gulma</i>	2/25/32
7.	<i>Palasha Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Raktaja Gulma</i>	2/25/60
8.	<i>Yava Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Mutrakrichchha</i>	2/27/33
9.	<i>Patala Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Mutraghata</i>	2/28/30
10.	<i>Arani Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Shopha</i>	2/33/69
11.	<i>Kadali Kshara</i>	<i>Katipaya Lepa</i>	<i>Sidhma</i>	2/36/125
12.	<i>Mayuraka (Apamarga) Kshara</i>	<i>Sidhmahara Yoga</i>	<i>Sidhma</i>	2/36/212
13.	<i>Jalakumbhi Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Mukharoga</i>	3/1/Mukharoga/65
14.	<i>Kakadani, Kantakari, Kakajangha, Bruhati, Kadambapushpi, Mandari, Lamba, Shukanasa Kshara</i>	<i>Kakadanyadi Kshara</i>	<i>Shlipada</i>	3/2/16

Sharangadhara Samhita

Acharya Sharangdhara categorizes *Kshara* into *Paniya* and *Pratisaraniya Kshara* with their characteristics. A general method for *Kshara* preparation is provided, but specific details about the names of the plants used, the timing of their collection, and the preparation method for *Mridu*, *Madhyama* and *Tikshna Kshara* are not mentioned.³⁰

Table No.11: Different *Kshara* mentioned in *Sharangadhara Samhita*

Sr.no	Name of <i>Kshara</i>	Name of Formulation	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Yava Kshara, Svarjika Kshara</i>	<i>Ksharadvaya Churna</i>	<i>Sharkara, Ashmari</i>	M. Kh. 6/25
2.	<i>Balamulaka Kshara</i>	<i>Kshara Taila</i>	<i>Karnaroga</i>	M. Kh. 9/174
3.	<i>Rambha (Kadali)</i>	<i>Karviradi Taila</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	M. Kh. 9/187
4.	<i>Palasha Kshara</i>	<i>Lomashatana Yoga</i>	<i>Lomashatana</i>	Ut. Kh. 11/38
5.	<i>Apamarga Kshara</i>	<i>Apamarga Kshara Taila</i>	<i>Karnastrava</i>	Ut. 11/144

Bhavaprakasha Samhita

Acharya Bhavmishra has mentioned the uses of *Kshara* in the preparation of different formulations.

Table No. 12: Different *Kshara* mentioned in Bhavaprakasha Samhita

Sr.no	Name of <i>Kshara</i>	Name of Formulation	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Chincha Tvaka Kshara</i>	<i>Suryashekhara Rasa</i>	<i>Vatakaphaja Jvara</i>	M. 1/475
2.	<i>Yava Kshara</i>	<i>Adrakadi Kalka</i>	<i>Varidosha</i>	M. 1/903
3.	<i>Tila, Mushka, Palasha, Kokilaksha, Shigru Kshara</i>	<i>Brihada Agnimukha Churna</i>	<i>Ajirna, Gulma, Pliharoga, Vatarakta</i>	M. 6/47
4.	<i>Svarjika Kshara</i>	<i>Agnikumara Rasa</i>	<i>Visuchika, Shula, Vataroga</i>	M. 6/87
5.	<i>Rambha (Kadali) Kshara</i>	<i>Brihada Shankha Vati</i>	<i>Ajirna, Shula, Alasaka</i>	M. 6/98
6.	<i>Kushmanda Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Shula</i>	M. 30/56
7.	<i>Ketaki Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Vataja Gulma</i>	M. 32/25
8.	<i>Mulaka Kshara, Haridra Kshara</i>	<i>Lepa Yoga</i>	<i>Arbuda</i>	M. 44/53

Yogatarangini

Vahnisama (fire like) property of *Yava Kshara* and *Svarjika Kshara* are mentioned in this text.³¹ Various *Kshara* utilized in different treatments in this text are listed below.

Table No. 13: Different *Kshara* mentioned in Yogatarangini

Sr.no	Name of <i>Kshara</i>	Name of Formulation	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Yava Kshara, Svarjika Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Gulma</i>	8/57
2.	<i>Chincha Kshara</i>	<i>Sheetari Rasa</i>	<i>Ajirna, Jvara</i>	20/158
3.	<i>Chanaka Kshara</i>	<i>Kravyada Rasa</i>	<i>Agnimandhya</i>	24/43
4.	<i>Asvattha, Snuhi, Apamarga, Arka Kshara</i>	<i>Shankha Vati</i>	<i>Shula, Grahani, Jathararoga</i>	24/51
5.	<i>Tilanala Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Mutradosha</i>	50/7
6.	<i>Shushka Mulaka, Shunthi Kshara</i>	<i>Laghu Shunthi Taila</i>	<i>Agnimandhya</i>	71/16

Yogaratnakara

Preparatory method of *Kshara* is same as mentioned in Sharangadhara Samhita.³² Approximately 13 *Kshara* are mentioned in this text as listed below.

Table No. 14: Different *Kshara* mentioned in Yogaratnakara

Sr. no	Name of <i>Kshara</i>	Name of Formulation	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Bhallataka Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Hridaroga, Pandu, Grahani</i>	Pu. <i>Grahani</i> /2
2.	<i>Yava Kshara</i>	<i>Arshakuthara Rasa</i>	<i>Arsha</i>	Pu. <i>Agnimandhya</i> /1
3.	<i>Chincha, Ashvtttha, Apamarga, Snuhi, Arka Kshara</i>	<i>Shankha Vati</i>	<i>Shula, Anaha, Ajirna</i>	Pu. <i>Ajirna Chi.</i> /1
4.	<i>Palasha Kshara</i>	<i>Palasha Kshara Ghrita</i>	<i>Raktaja Gulma</i>	Ut. <i>Gulma Chi.</i> 1
5.	<i>Ankola, Tila Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Mutrakrichchha</i>	Ut. <i>Mutrakrichchha</i> /1
6.	<i>Kadali Kshara</i>	<i>Tila Ksharadi Taila</i>	<i>Ashmari</i>	Ut. <i>Mutrakrichchha</i> /2
7.	<i>Eranda, Dravanti</i>	<i>Dravtinaga Vati</i>	<i>Yakrita Pliha</i>	Ut. <i>Udara</i> /4

Bhaishajya Ratnavali

The method of preparation is same as given in Chakradatta.³³ *Danti Kshara* is mentioned as a *Pratinidhi Dravya* for *Chitraka* and *Tila Kshara* in the *Shodhana* of *Haratala*. Different *Kshara* found in this text are listed below.

Table No. 15: Different *Kshara* mentioned in Bhaishajya Ratnavali

Sr. no	Name of <i>Kshara</i>	Name of Formulation	Indication	Reference
1.	<i>Danti Kshara</i>	-	-	4/16
2.	<i>Tila Kshara</i>	-	-	5/1063
3.	<i>Apamarga Kshara</i>	<i>Apamargadi Lepa</i>	<i>Lingarsha</i>	9/16
4.	<i>Mushkaka, Shigru, Kokilaksha, Palasha Kshara</i>	<i>Brihatagnimukha Churna</i>	<i>Udararoga, Ashthila, Antravridhi</i>	10/70
5.	<i>Chinchatvaka Kshara</i>	<i>Agnisandipana Rasa</i>	<i>Mandagni, Ajirna, Amlapita</i>	10/133
6.	<i>Arka, Snuhi, Ashvattha, Kshara</i>	<i>Pashupata Rasa</i>	<i>Kaphaja Roga</i>	10/169
7.	<i>Mulaka Kshara</i>	<i>Gandhaka Vati</i>	<i>Ajirna</i>	10/243
8.	<i>Svarjika, Ketaki Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Vataja Gulma</i>	32/15
9.	<i>Kadali, Amalaka Kshara</i>	<i>Anandayoga</i>	<i>Sharkara, Ashmari</i>	36/24
10.	<i>Eranda Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Medovridhi</i>	39/20
11.	<i>Talapushpa Kshara</i>	<i>Talapushpa Ksharadi Yoga</i>	<i>Pliharoga</i>	41/18

12.	<i>Putika Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Yakrita Pliha Roga</i>	41/61
13.	<i>Vrusha, Kushmanda, Varshabhu Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Yakrita Pliha Roga</i>	41/115
14.	<i>Padmanala Kshara</i>	Used as single <i>Kshara</i>	<i>Padminikantaka</i>	60/26
15.	<i>Shunthi Kshara</i>	<i>Kshara Taila</i>	<i>Karnaroga, Krimi</i>	62/18

A total of 106 plant-origin and 18 animal-origin *Kshara* were identified from 15 classical texts. Among them, 84 are intended for internal use, 14 for external use and 17 for both internal and external administration, as tabulated in table no. 16.

Table No. 16: category wise distribution of various *Kshara*

Sr.no.	Name of category	Origin	Name of <i>Kshara</i>
1.	Internal	Plant	<i>Utpala, Mrunala, Priyangu, Madhooka, Asana, Bilva, Agnimantha, Shyonaka, Bala, Tilanal, Ashwagandha, Eranda, Surasa Mushkaka, Putikaranj, Kakadani, Kakajangha, Bruhati, Kantakari, Lamba, Kadambapushpi, Mandari, Shukanasa, Danti, Dravanti, Trivrita / Shyama, Nili, Satala, Shankhini, Arjuna, Dhava, Jivanti, Kanaka, Vasa, Vishala, Kokila, Shati, Pippali, Patala, Kasamarda, Shalaparni, Prishnaparni, Gokshura, Arka, Patha, Rasna, Snuhi, Paribhadra, Karavira, Rishabha, Tintuka, Hatha, Palashabija, Shigru, Vatyala, Manakanda, Pushkaramula, Brahmanayashtika, Punarnava, Himstra, Chinchu, Kushmanda, Chanaka, Ashwattha, Ankola, Eranda, Amalaka, Putika (69)</i>
		Animal	<i>Mayurapadanala, Shakala Shallka, Kurara Roma, Chasha Roma, Aja-Avi Ashthi, Ek-Dvishapha Charma, Ashthi, Khura, Samudrashukti, Gramyapashu Shakrita, Krauncha Ashthi, Hasti, Shukara, Ushtra and Khara Ashthi (15)</i>
2.	External	Plant	<i>Malati Koraka, Surana, Jivaka, Mudga, Masha, Narikela Ashthi, Tala, Vamsha, Karira, Chavya, Jalakumbhi, (13)</i>
		Animal	<i>Gajamala (1)</i>
3.	Internal and External	Plant	<i>Svarjika, Yava, Tila, Kadali, Apamarga, Palasha, Mulaka, Mulaka, Kokilaksha, Arka, Bhallataka, Chitraka, Shunthi, Haridra, Padma (15)</i>
		Animal	<i>Gomaya, Ajashakrita (2)</i>
4.	Use not found		<i>Kutaja, Tilvaka, Gunja, Vibhitaka, Indravrishta, Saptachhada, 4 types of Koshataki, Aragavadha, Asphota (9)</i>

The total number of different individual *Kshara* is highest in Ashtanga Samgraha (47), followed by Sushruta Samhita (44), while the minimum is observed in Kashyapa Samhita (2), which mentions only *Yava*

and *Svarjika Kshara*. The total number of different *Kshara* are found in classical texts are listed in table no. 17.

Table No. 17: Listing of total number of *Kshara* in classical text

Sr. no.	Name of classical text	Total number of individual <i>Kshara</i>
1.	Charaka Samhita	33
2.	Susruta Samhita	44
3.	Kashyapa Samhita	02
4.	Harita Samhita	28
5.	Bhela Samhita	07
6.	Ashtanga Samgraha	47
7.	Ashtanga Hridaya	20
8.	Chakradatta	21
9.	Vangasena Samhita	18
10.	Gada Nigraha	32
11.	Sharangadhara Samhita	06
12.	Bhavaprakasha Samhita	13
13.	Yoga Tarangini	11
14.	Yoga Ratnakara	13
15.	Bhaishjya Ratnavali	24

Kshara used for therapeutic purpose, both internally and externally, as mentioned in various classical texts, are shown in graph no. 1. The highest number of *Kshara* indicated for therapeutic use are found in Astanga Samgraha (47).

Graph No. 1: Total number of *Kshara* as therapeutic use in different text

Various formulations of *Kshara* are mentioned for internal use in a wide range of disorders, including *Krimi*, *Kushtha*, *Raktapitta*, *Gulma*, *Pandu*, *Grahani*, *Shotha*, *Jalodara*, *Udararoga*, *Hridroga*, *Vatavikara*, *Svasa*, *Kasa*, *Slipada*, *Yakrita-Pliharoga*, *Shula*, *Vibandha*, *Anaha*, *Ajirna*, *Mutraroga*, *Yoniroga*, *Apachi*, *Amlapitta*, *Vridhhi*, *Arsha*, *Arbuda*, *Medovridhhi*, *Galaganda*, *Sidhma*, *Ashmari*, and *Sharkara*, a total of 32 disease conditions. For external application, they are employed in the management of *Kushtha*, *Karnaroga*, *Netraroga*, *Svitra* and *Vrana*. In *Arsha*, *Arbuda Vidradhi* and *Vatavikara* they are used for both internal and external application. Various internal dosage forms of *Kshara* include *Churna*, *Vati/ Guti/ Guggulu*, *Taila*, *Ghrita*, *Yavagu*, *Panaka*, *Leha*, *Agada*, *Avaleha/ Guda* and *Rasa Yoga*, whereas external applications were found as *Ksharasutra*, *Lepa*, *Varti*, *Taila*, *Basti* and *Ghrita*.

CONCLUSION

Kshara Kalpana stands as a unique and potent formulation within Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals, rooted in ancient wisdom and elaborated primarily in classical texts. Among these, Sushruta Samhita provides the most detailed and foundational insights, particularly due to its surgical context. The present review highlights that a total of 15 Ayurvedic texts mentioned *Kshara* in various formulations, with variations in the number, type, and source of *Kshara Dravya*. Plantbased *Kshara* dominate, while animal- and mineral-origin *Kshara* are less frequently described. Ashtanga Samgraha records the highest number of individual *Kshara*, indicating a broader therapeutic application during that period. This critical textual and historical analysis reveals the evolutionary significance and therapeutic versatility of *Kshara Kalpana*. It not only underscores the depth of Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals but also opens up avenues for further research to validate and utilize these traditional formulations in modern contexts.

REFERENCES

1. *Acharya Agnivesha*, Charaka samhita of *Acharya Charaka*, Dridhabala krit, edited by Pt. Kashinath Shastri and Dr. Gorakhnath Chaturvedi. Chikitsasthana, Ch. 15, Ver. 172, Varanasi: Chaukhamba Bharti Academy; 2021. pg.430
2. *Acharya Agnivesha*, Charaka samhita of *Acharya Charaka*, Dridhabala krit, edited by Pt. Kashinath Shastri and Dr. Gorakhnath Chaturvedi. Chikitsasthana, Ch. 15, Ver. 185, Varanasi: Chaukhamba Bharti Academy; 2021. pg.431
3. Govind Das Sen, Bhaishajya Ratnavali with Vidyotani hindi commentary of Kaaviraja Ambikadatta Shashtri, Ch. 10, Ver. 187, 18th Edition, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Prakashana; Reprint: 2019. pg.327.
4. *Acharya Shimad Vagbhata*, Ashtanga Hridaya, edited by Bramhmanand Tripathi, Chikitsasthana, Ch. 15, Ver. 14-29, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Prakashan; Reprint 2017 Delhi. pg.748
5. *Acharya Agnivesha*, Charaka samhita of *Acharya Charaka*, Dridhabala krit, edited by Pt. Kashinath Shastri and Dr. Gorakhnath Chaturvedi. Sutrasthana, Ch. 169, verse. 35, Varanasi: Chaukhamba Bharti Academy; 2021,pg. 420
6. *Acharya Agnivesha*, Charaka samhita of *Acharya Charaka*, Dridhabala krit, edited by Pt. Kashinath Shastri and Dr. Gorakhnath Chaturvedi. Sutrasthana, Ch. 11, verse. 55, Varanasi: Chaukhamba Bharti Academy; 2021,pg. 209
7. *Acharya Agnivesha*, Charaka samhita of *Acharya Charaka*, Dridhabala krit, edited by Pt. Kashinath Shastri and Dr. Gorakhnath Chaturvedi. Sutrasthana, Ch. 1, verse. 74, Varanasi: Chaukhamba Bharti Academy; 2021,pg. 36
8. *Acharya Agnivesha*, Charaka samhita of *Acharya Charaka*, Dridhabala krit, edited by Pt. Kashinath Shastri and Dr. Gorakhnath Chaturvedi. Vimanasthana, Ch. 8, verse. 142, Varanasi: Chaukhamba Bharti Academy; 2021,pg. 700

9. *Acharya* Agnivesha, Charaka samhita of *Acharya* Charaka, Dridhabala krit, edited by Pt. Kashinath Shastri and Dr. Gorakhnath Chaturvedi. Vimanasthana, Ch. 1, verse. 17, Varanasi: Chaukhamba Bharti Academy; 2021,pg. 603
10. *Acharya* Sushruta, Sushruta Samhita, edited by Shastri Ambikadatta, Sutra Sthana Ch. 11, Varanasi:Chaukhambha Sanskrita Samsthana; Reprint 2017, pg 45
11. *Acharya* Sushruta, Sushruta Samhita, edited by Shastri Ambikadatta, Sutra Sthana Ch. 11, Ver. 9 Varanasi:Chaukhambha Sanskrita Samsthana; Reprint 2017 , pg 46
12. *Acharya* Sushruta, Sushruta Samhita, edited by Shastri Ambikadatta, Sutra Sthana Ch. 11, Ver. 12 Varanasi:Chaukhambha Sanskrita Samsthana; Reprint 2017 , 47
13. *Acharya Kashyapa, Kashyapa Samhita*, edited by Dr. Hemaraj Sharma, Chikitsa sthan, 4, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrita Samsthana; Reprint 2021 pg 159
14. *Acharya* Harita, Harita Samhita, edited by Vaidya Jaymini Pandey, Prathama Sthana/6 verse 17, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Vishwabharati;2022 pg 43
15. *Acharya* Harita, Harita Samhita, edited by Vaidya Jaymini Pandey, Prathama Sthana/2, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Vishwabharati;2022 Pg 10
16. *Acharya* Harita, Harita Samhita, edited by Vaidya Jaymini Pandey, Trutiya Sthana/1, verse 11, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Vishwabharati;2022 Pg 506
17. Maharsi Bhela, Bhelasamhita, edited with Hindi commentary by Sri Abhay Katyayan, Sutra Sthan.cha.28.verse.15. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharti Prakashan, Reprint 2009, Pg 142
18. Maharsi Bhela, Bhelasamhita, edited with Hindi commentary by Sri Abhay Katyayan, Sutra Sthan.cha.28.verse.16s. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharti Prakashan, Reprint 2009, Pg 142
19. Maharsi Bhela, Bhelasamhita, edited with Hindi commentary by Sri Abhay Katyayan, *Vimana Sthana*.cha.1.verse.18. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharti Prakashan, Reprint 2009, Pg 178
20. Vagbhata, Astanga Samgraha, Ch.39/10,hindi commentary of Kaviraja Atridev Gupt, Chaukhambha Krishnadas Academy, Varanasi, reprint 2019 pg. 245
21. *Acharya* Shimad Vagbhata, Ashtanga Hridaya, edited by Bramhmanand Tripathi, Sutrasthana, Ch. 30, Ver. 8-21, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Prakashan; Reprint 2017 Delhi. pg.329
22. *Acharya* Chakrapanidatta, Chakradutta, with Vaidyaprabha Hindi commentary by Dr.Indradeva Tripathi, edited by
23. Prof.Ramanath Dwivedi. Reprint, Ch.5. Ver.143. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Bhavana, Reprint 2019. pg.65 ²³*Acharya* Chakrapanidatta, Chakradutta, with Vaidyaprabha Hindi commentary by Dr.Indradeva Tripathi, edited by Prof.Ramanath Dwivedi. Reprint, Ch.5.Ver.147. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Bhavana;2019. pg. 66
24. *Acharya* Chakrapanidatta, Chakradutta, with Vaidyaprabha Hindi commentary by Dr.Indradeva Tripathi, edited by Prof.Ramanath Dwivedi. Reprint, Ch.5.Ver.156. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Bhavana;2019. pg. 66
25. *Acharya* Chakrapanidatta, Chakradutta, with Vaidyaprabha Hindi commentary by Dr.Indradeva Tripathi, edited by Prof.Ramanath Dwivedi. Reprint, Ch.5. Ver.148. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Bhavana;2019. pg.66
26. Vangasena, Vangasena Samhita, edited and translated by Pandit Hariharaprasad Pandya, cha 21, verse 372-384, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Prakashan; Reprint 2016 pg 307
27. *Acharya* Shodhala, Gada Nigraha by dr. Indradev Tripathi, 3rd part, cha 6, Verse 16-19, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrita Sansthana; Reprint 2022, pg 327
28. *Acharya* Shodhala, Gada Nigraha by dr. Indradev Tripathi, 2nd part, *Kayachikitsa Khanda*, cha 4, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrita Sansthana; Reprint 2022, pg 231-235

29. *Acharya* Shodhala, Gada Nigraha by dr. Indradev Tripathi, 3rd part, cha 3, Verse 50, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrita Sansthana; Reprint 2022, pg 294
30. *Acharya* Sharangadhara, Sharangadhara Samhitha, edited by Brahmanand Bhushana, Madhyama Khanda, Ch. 11, Ver. 101-105, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharti Prakashana; Reprint 2021. pg. 185
31. Yoga Tarangini, *Taranga* 1, verse 57, traslated by Mathur Pandit Kanaiyalal, Reprint, Mumbai:Khemaraja Krushnadas Prakashana; 2018;81
32. Anonymous, Yoga Ratnakara, *Purvardha Abhava Varga Kshara Kalpana*, with Commentry “*Vidhyotani*”, edited by Vaidya lakshmipati Shashtri,Chaukhambha orientelia, Varanasi,2010 pg. 170
33. Govind Das Sen, Bhaishajya Ratnavali with Vidyotani hindi commentary of Kaaviraja Ambikadatta Shashtri, Ch. 10, Ver. 262-270, 18th Edition, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Prakashana; Reprint: 2019. pg.327.